

PREVENTION OF PERIODONTITIS DISEASE IN MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN

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Relevance of the topic: Today, one of the most common stomatological diseases is periodontitis, which is an inflammatory disease of the gums, which over time leads to atrophy of bone and connective tissue of the gums, resulting in tooth decay and spontaneous loss of teeth.

In general, bad habits and general diseases, smoking, diabetes, gastrointestinal diseases, diseases of the cardiovascular system, stress, squeezing the gums due to the formation of alloy stones around the teeth, defects in the development of the jaw and palate, improper growth of teeth, teeth It is caused by diseases such as crooked position and mouth breathing.

Purpose of work: as the purpose of the work, the occurrence, causes and spread of periodontitis in middle-aged women living in the city of Urganch were studied.

Results obtained: The results of the investigation showed that periodontitis is mainly found in women aged 30-35, and the cause of the disease is that they do not follow the rules of dental hygiene in time.

Also, as a complication, the loss of teeth, as well as the absorption of toxins from microbes that caused periodontitis, cardiovascular system diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, and respiratory system diseases were also detected.

Conclusions: In conclusion, it can be said that periodontitis disease is mainly due to non-observance of dental hygiene, and as a result, teeth fall out on their own, and as a result of the microbes in the oral cavity, other diseases occur in our living body, that is, diseases of the cardiovascular system, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, and respiratory system diseases.

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